

Quantitative Determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in Pharmaceutical Raw Materials by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography.

Derouicha MATMOUR^{1,2*}, Khalil Fateh Eddine HASSAM³, Nadjib HAMOUM³, Amel CHENAF², Khadidja YANALLAH², Yassine MERAD², Nassima HAMDI ZIANI³.

¹Therapeutic and Pharmaceutical Chemistry Laboratory, Pharmacy Department, Faculty of Medicine, University of Sidi Bel-Abbes, 22000, Algeria.

²Central Laboratory, University Hospital Center of Sidi Bel-Abbes, 22000, Algeria.

³Quality control laboratory, WanyLab, 16002 Algiers, Algeria.

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this work was to apply a HPLC method for the quantitative determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical raw material in seven samples collected from seven pharmaceutical industries installed in Algeria. A liquid chromatography apparatus HPLC-UV device (Thermo Scientific Dionex UltiMate 3000 Rapid Separation LC systems, Germany) equipped with an automatic injector and UV/Vis detector was used, the chromatographic conditions were regled at temperature: 40 °C, flow rate: 1.5 mL/min, injection volume: 10 µl, Column: C₁₈ (5 µm x 4.6 mm x 250 mm) and the wavelength λ: 278 nm. The mobile phase was composed of 13 volumes of acetonitrile mixed with 87 volumes of phosphoric acid solution at 2.45 g/L, previously adjusted to pH 3.0 with triethylamine. The standard solution and the test solutions were prepared at 0.5 mg/mL. All samples had an anhydrous Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride content meeting the standards, except C5 sample which had a content of 97.6 % lower than the standard wich can be due to the sample degradation. The applied HPLC method showed to be adequate to quantify Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in the pharmaceutical raw materials.

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1. Introduction

Fluoroquinolones comprise a series of broad spectrum synthetic antibacterial agents derived from nalidixic acid. They were discovered casually in 1962 and since then are essentially used in the treatment of several infectious diseases [1-4]. Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride [1-cyclo-propyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolone carboxylic acid] (Fig. 1) is a second-generation fluoroquinolone antimicrobial agent with a wide spectrum of activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [5]. It is the drug of choice for the treatment of urinary tract infections, acute uncomplicated cystitis in females, chronic bacterial prostatitis, lower respiratory tract infections, acute sinusitis, skin structure infections, bone and joint infections, infectious diarrhoea, typhoid fever, uncomplicated cervical and urethral gonorrhoea [6]. It is believed

* Corresponding author: Derouicha MATMOUR Tel.: +213 659833444
E-mail address: drmatmour24@hotmail.fr

that the mode of action of fluoroquinolones is through binding DNA-gyrase enzyme [7]. There are several analytical methods described in the literature for the determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride based on high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) techniques [8-11]. HPLC is described as the official method for analysis of Ciprofloxacin in the United States Pharmacopoeia, in the European Pharmacopoeia, in the British Pharmacopoeia and in the Brazilian Pharmacopoeia [12-15].

In Algeria, Ciprofloxacin is produced by more than 18 pharmaceutical producers [16]. The main objective of this work was to apply a HPLC method for the quantitative determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical raw material in seven samples collected from seven pharmaceutical industries installed in Algeria.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride [21].

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Collection of samples

Seven samples of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride raw material were collected from seven pharmaceutical industries installed in Algeria by referring to the Algerian drug nomenclature dated the 31st December 2014 [16]. The samples are collected during the period from 1st April 2015 to 31st December 2016. The compendium covers not only the raw material but also the following necessary information (origin, supplier/manufacturer, expiration date, analysis certificate, synthesis route, Drug Master File.....etc) [17-20]. The samples weren't expired and we labeled them as follows: C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6 and C7. They were stored at room temperature, protected from light and humidity and analyzed prior to their expiration date. For some samples, we didn't receive all the necessary informations.

2.2 Quantitative determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride by HPLC

A liquid chromatography apparatus HPLC-UV device (Thermo Scientific Dionex UltiMate 3000 Rapid Separation LC systems, Germany) equipped with an automatic injector and UV/Vis detector was used, the chromatographic conditions were regled at temperature: 40 °C, flow rate: 1.5 mL/min, injection volume: 10 µl, Column: C₁₈ (5 µm x 4.6 mm x 250 mm) and the wavelength λ: 278 nm [21-23]. The mobile phase was composed of 13 volumes of acetonitrile mixed with 87 volumes of phosphoric acid solution at 2.45 g/L, previously adjusted to pH 3.0 with triethylamine.

The standard solution and the test solutions were prepared at 0.5 mg/mL [22].

The Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride SCR purchased from the Eur Ph (Strasbourg, France) was used as a reference standard for the assay [24].

3. Results and discussion

3.2 Quantitative determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride by HPLC

The Fig. 2 and 3 show respectively the obtained chromatograms with the standard solutions. The Fig. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 show respectively the obtained chromatograms with the test solutions of C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6 and C7 samples. The Table 1 summarizes the content results of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride "As it is" and in

"Anhydrous substance" by HPLC of the various samples of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride analyzed as well as the standards required by the Eur Ph.

According to the four injections of weight 1 standard and the two injections of weight 2 verification standard, the Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride peak was detected and its retention time was around 9 min, a value close to that required by the Eur Ph [21]. The coefficient of variation between the four injections was 0.98 %; it was less than 2 %, which confirms that this analysis method is reproducible. According to the Eur Ph standards [22], the content of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in "Anhydrous substance" must be between 98.0 % and 102.0 %. All samples had an anhydrous Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride content meeting the standards, except C5 sample which had a content of 97.6 % lower than the standard which can be due to the sample degradation (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Chromatograms of standard solution weight 1 (4 injections).

Fig. 3. Chromatograms of standard solution weight 2 (2 injections).

Fig. 4. Chromatograms of C1 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 5. Chromatograms of C2 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 6. Chromatograms of C3 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 7. Chromatograms of C4 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 8. Chromatograms of C5 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 9. Chromatograms of C6 sample (4 injections).

Fig. 10. Chromatograms of C7 sample (4 injections).

Table 1. Content of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride "As it is" and in "Anhydrous substance" by HPLC.

Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride Sample	Weight (mg)	Pic Area (mAU.min)	"As it is" Content (%)	Water Content (%)	"Anhydrous Substance" Content (%)	Average (%)	Norms in "Anhydrous Substance" (%)
C1- P1-1	50,3	358,743	94,87	6,72	101,7	101,2	98.0 à 102.0
C1- P1-2	50,3	358,058	94,69	6,72	101,5		
C1- P2-1	50,2	354,835	94,03	6,72	100,8		
C1- P2-2	50,2	354,874	94,04	6,72	100,8		
C2- P1-1	50,7	352,952	92,61	6,25	98,8	99,0	
C2- P1-2	50,7	353,395	92,72	6,25	98,9		
C2- P2-1	50,4	352,151	92,95	6,25	99,1		
C2- P2-2	50,4	351,754	92,84	6,25	99,0		
C3- P1-1	50,5	364,761	96,08	6,55	102,8	101,0	
C3- P1-2	50,5	364,776	96,09	6,55	102,8		
C3- P2-1	50,5	351,111	92,49	6,55	99,0		
C3- P2-2	50,5	352,012	92,72	6,55	99,2		

C4- P1-1	50,5	354,656	93,42	7,21	100,7	
C4- P1-2	50,5	356,580	93,93	7,21	101,2	100,2
C4- P2-1	50,7	352,181	92,40	7,21	99,6	
C4- P2-2	50,7	351,840	92,31	7,21	99,5	
C5- P1-1	50,3	344,400	91,08	6,72	97,6	
C5- P1-2	50,3	344,664	91,15	6,72	97,7	97,6
C5- P2-1	50,2	343,915	91,13	6,72	97,7	
C5- P2-2	50,2	342,804	90,84	6,72	97,4	
C6- P1-1	50,0	348,492	92,72	6,24	98,9	98.0 à 102.0
C6- P1-2	50,0	348,601	92,74	6,24	98,9	99,2
C6- P2-1	50,4	353,162	93,21	6,24	99,4	
C6- P2-2	50,4	353,650	93,34	6,24	99,6	
C7- P1-1	50,4	344,117	90,82	6,51	97,1	
C7- P1-2	50,4	344,496	90,92	6,51	97,3	98,0
C7- P2-1	50,4	349,168	92,16	6,51	98,6	
C7- P2-2	50,4	350,217	92,43	6,51	98,9	

4. Conclusion

The quantitative determination of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical raw materials was realized by HPLC in seven samples collected from seven pharmaceutical industries installed in Algeria. All samples had an anhydrous Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride content meeting the standards, except C5 sample which had a content of 97.6 % lower than the standard which can be due to the sample degradation. The applied HPLC method showed to be adequate to quantify Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride in the pharmaceutical raw materials.

Disclosure of interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

- [1] Bertino J and Fish D. Safety profiles of the fluoroquinolones. *Clin Ther.* 2000; 22:798-817.
- [2] Fierens C, Hillaert S, Van Den Bossche W. The qualitative and quantitative determination of quinolones of first and second generation by capillary electrophoresis. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2000; 22:763-772.
- [3] Marzo A, Dal Bo L. Chromatography as an analytical tool for selected antibiotic classes: a reappraisal addressed to pharmacokinetic applications. *J Chromatogr A.* 2002; 812:17-34.
- [4] Arteseros JAH, Barbosa J, Compano R, Prat MD. Analysis of quinolone residues in edible animal products. *J Chromatogr A.* 2002; 945:1-24.
- [5] Kassab NM, Singh AK, Kedor-Hackmam ERM, Santoro MIRM. Quantitative determination of ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin in pharmaceutical preparations by high performance liquid chromatography. *Braz J Pharm Sci.* 2005; 41(4):507-513.
- [6] Goossens H, Ferech M, Coenen S, Stephens P. Comparison of outpatient systemic antibacterial use in 2004 in the United States and 27 European countries. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2007; 44(8):1091-1095.
- [7] Wise R, Andrews JM, Edwards LJ. In vitro activity of Bay 09867, a new quinoline derivative, compared with those of

- other antimicrobial agents. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 1983; 23:559-564.
- [8] Husain S, Khalid S, Nagaraju V, Nageswara Rao R. High performance liquid chromatographic separation and determination of small amounts of process impurities of ciprofloxacin in bulk drugs and formulations. *J Chromatogr.* 1995; 705:380-384.
- [9] Zotou A, Miltiadou N. Sensitive LC determination of ciprofloxacin in pharmaceutical preparations and biological fluids with fluorescence detection. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2002; 28: 559-568.
- [10] Kassab NM, Singh AK, Kedor-Hackmam ERM, Santoro MIRM. Quantitative determination of ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin in pharmaceutical preparations by high performance liquid chromatography. *Braz J Pharm Sci.* 2005; 41(4):507-513.
- [11] Cazedey ECL, Perez DP, Perez JP, Salgado, HRN. LC Assay for Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride Ophthalmic Solution. *Chromatographia.* 2009; 69:S241-S244.
- [12] United States Pharmacopoeia (USP); 40th ed. United States Pharmacopoeia Convention: Rockville, 2017.
- [13] European Pharmacopoeia, 8th edition. Council of Europe. Strasbourg, France; 2015.
- [14] British Pharmacopoeia. London: Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 2016.
- [15] Brazilian Pharmacopoeia. 15.ed. São Paulo: Atheneu, 2015.
- [16] Ministry of Health, Population and Hospital Reform, Pharmaceutical Products Directorate, Registration under-direction. Algerian medicines nomenclature; 2014. [Available at: <http://www.sante.gov.dz/images/pharmacy/nationalnomenclatureofpharmaceuticalproduct>. Accessed January 8, 2015].
- [17] Synthesis route of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride. Batch: CICA4066. Chemo S.A. Lugano Branch. Switzerland.
- [18] Synthesis route of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride Monohydrate. Batch: 10271610. Dr Reddy's Laboratories LTD. India.
- [19] Synthesis procedure of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride. Batch: 120801. Pharmaceutical Co. LTD. China.
- [20] Synthesis route of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride. Batch: KOFA006. Dr Reddy's Laboratories LTD. India.
- [21] European Pharmacopoeia, 8th edition. Council of Europe. Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride Monograph. Related substances. Strasbourg, France; 2015:1896-97.
- [22] European Pharmacopoeia, 8th edition. Council of Europe. Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride Monograph. Dosage. Strasbourg, France; 2015:1897.
- [23] European Pharmacopoeia 8th edition. Council of Europe. Physical and physicochemical methods. Liquid chromatography. Strasbourg, France; 2015: 48-50.
- [24] European Directorate for the Quality of Medicines and Healthcare. European Pharmacopoeia. Fact Sheet: Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride SCR. Catalog code: C2190000. October 31, 2014; 1-2. Available at: https://crs.edqm.eu/db/4DCGI/db/4DCGI/leaflet?leaflet=C21_900006 [Accessed March 27, 2015].